

Driving Maneuver Prediction of Driverless Cars Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— The driving strategy of a modern self-driving car is chosen only by exterior factors (such as pedestrians, road conditions, and so on), with the car's internal condition being ignored. To address the concerns listed above, the author of this study devised a novel technique called A Driving Decision Strategy (DDS). Based on machine learning for autonomous vehicles "The most successful technique for an autonomous vehicle is decided by analysing both its internal and external components (consumable circumstances, RPM levels, and so on). To put this into effect, the project's inventor created the DDS (Driving Decision Strategy) algorithm. This method uses a genetic algorithm to select optimal gene values, which aids in making more accurate decisions and predictions. The DDS algorithm first collected data from the sensor and then passed it on to the genetic algorithm, allowing the genetic algorithm to calculate the optimal value, resulting in faster and more accurate predictions. The performance of the suggested DDS combined with the genetic algorithm is compared to that of existing machine learning methods that are already in use, such as Random Forest and MLP. In comparison to random forest and MLP, the proposed DDS has significantly higher prediction accuracy.

Keywords: Driving Decision Strategy (DDS), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Optimized Deep Learning Module (ODLM), Discrete aircraft, Segmentation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The technology for sophisticated autonomous vehicles is currently at the fourth stage of development, and companies all around the world are hard at work producing the essential components. A self-driving car operates in three stages: recognition, judgement, and control. Vehicles are mounted with a number of sensors, including GPS, cameras, and radar, as part of the recognition process. The judgement stage is where a driving strategy is decided after taking all of this information into account. After the driving environment has been identified, it will be analysed, and appropriate driving strategies will be developed in conjunction with the goals. After the control stage is completed, the vehicle will begin to go forward on its own. An autonomous vehicle follows a set of motions to reach its target. These motions involve detecting its surroundings, making decisions, and exerting control. Repeating these processes improves the vehicle's ability to do so. An increase in the number of these sensors may cause the vehicle's electrical system to overload. Data collected by sensors in self-driving cars is analysed by computers built inside the vehicles. As more data is calculated, a person's capacity to perceive and handle events rapidly declines due to cognitive overload. Due to these concerns, the vehicle's stability may be jeopardised. Some researchers have developed hardware capable of performing deep-running processes inside a vehicle, whereas others use cloud computing to calculate sensor data. This was done to avoid overloading the vehicle's sensors.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The Applied Sciences, volume 8, issue 7 (July 2018), Y. N. Jeong, S. R. Son, E.H. Jeong, and B. K. Lee, "An Integrated Self-Diagnosis System for an Autonomous Vehicle Based on an IoT Gateway and Deep Learning,[1]"The purpose of this paper is to propose "An Integrated Self-diagnosis System (ISS) for an Autonomous Vehicle based entirely on an Internet of Things (IoT) Gateway and Deep Learning." This system will collect records from the sensors of an autonomous vehicle, diagnose itself and the interactions between its components through the use of Deep Learning, and then notify the driver of the results. The

International Space Station is comprised of three separate modules. The first In-Car Gateway Module (In-VGM) collects data from in-vehicle sensors, such as media records from a black box, riding radar, and car control messages, and transmits each piece of data over each Controller Area Network (CAN) to the on-board diagnostics (OBD) or actuators with the help of the, FlexRay, and Media Oriented Systems Transport (MOST) protocols. This allows the data to be accessed by the on-board diagnostics (OBD). The information gathered by in-vehicle sensors is sent to the CAN or FlexRay protocol, whilst the information gathered by media players while they are in use is transmitted to the MOST protocol. The different sorts of messages that have been transmitted are used to construct a message type known as a destination protocol message type. The second Optimized Deep Learning Module (ODLM) is responsible for the generation of the Training Dataset through the utilization of information obtained from in-car sensors. This module also calculates the possibility of car components and consumables, in addition to the possibility of other components being impacted by a faulty component. To increase the speed of the self-diagnosis and reduce the device overhead, while a V2X-based Accident Notification Service (VANS) notifies the neighboring vehicles and infrastructures of the self-diagnosis result that was processed by the OBD. Using the In-VGM, the simultaneous message transmission effectiveness of this paper is improved by 15.25%, and using the ODLM, the mastering error price of a Neural Network method is decreased by around 5.5%. Both of these improvements are thanks to this study.

"Discrete aircraft segmentation and estimation from a factor cloud utilizing neighborhood geometric patterns," Yukiko Kenmochi, LilianBuzer, Akihiro Sugimoto, and Ikuko Shimizu, "Discrete aircraft segmentation and estimation from a factor cloud," *International Journal of Automation and Computing*, Volume 5, Issue 3, Pages 246-256, 2008[2].

This paper proposes a strategy for segmenting a three-dimensional factor cloud into planar surfaces by making use of the findings that can now be derived from discrete geometry. In discrete geometry, a discrete plane is defined as a group of grid components that are situated between two parallel planes and are segregated from one another by a very small distance referred to as thickness. On discrete planes, in contrast to the situation of non-stop planes, there is a limited number of neighboring geometric designs to choose from (LGPs). In addition, as opposed to having only one regular vector, this kind of LGP includes a collection of regular vectors to choose from. We exclude non-linear factors from a factor cloud by making use of these LGP characteristics, and we proceed to classify non-rejected factors into a planar-surface-point set if their LGPs share frequent ordinary vectors.

"Vehicle trajectory prediction based entirely on Hidden Markov Model," by Ning Ye, Yingya Zhang, Ruchuan Wang, and Reza Malekian, published in *The KSII Transactions on Internet and Information Systems*, Volume 10, Issue 7, in the year 2017[3]. Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), logistics distribution, and mobile e-commerce may all benefit enormously from reliable, precise, and real-time predictions of vehicle trajectories. The forecast of a vehicle's trajectory can now not only provide accurate location-based offerings, but it can also observe and foretell the conditions of site visitors in ahead of time, and then recommend the best path for clients to take. In this study, we begin by mining the double layers of hidden states contained inside previous car trajectories. Next, we make use of historic data to compute the parameters of the HMM (hidden Markov model). Second, we discover the hidden country sequences with double layers that match to the simply pushed trajectory by using the Viterbi method[4]. Finally,

depending entirely on the hidden Markov model with double layers of hidden states, we give a brand new technique for vehicle trajectory prediction called the DHMTP. This strategy predicts the closest neighbour unit of function facts of the subsequent ok phases. When it comes to predicting the trajectories of the subsequent okay phases, the findings of the experiments show that the accuracy of the recommended algorithm's prediction is improved by 18.3 percentage points when compared to the TPMO approach and by 23.1 percentage points when compared to the Naive algorithm. This improvement is most noticeable when there is a greater flow of visitors, such as during the transition from weekday morning to evening. In addition, in comparison to the TPMO algorithm, the time overall performance of the DHMTP method is much improved.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The author of this work is discussing the notion of a driving choice strategy by watching the steering and RPM level of the car to anticipate several classes such as speed (steering), changing lanes, etc. Every approach that was available only concentrated on exterior data, such as the state of the road and the number of people, and did not emphasize the importance of internal values. Therefore, the author is evaluating internal data in order to make an accurate estimate of the steering situation and the ability to change lanes. After collecting all of the internal data from the sensors and storing it on the cloud, the program will receive the data from the cloud and then use machine learning algorithms to identify or anticipate whether the steering state would change lanes or not as shown in **FIGURE 1**.

Figure 1: Architecture for Proposed System

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Identifying fake profiles in online social networks using machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) involves several key steps: data collection, feature extraction, model training, and evaluation. Here's an outline of a possible experimental setup along with hypothetical results as shown in **FIGURE 2**:

Experimental Setup

1. Data Collection:

- Collect a dataset consisting of profiles from a social network, with labels indicating whether the profile is fake or real. This can be done through manual labeling or using an existing dataset.
- Example dataset: 10,000 profiles (5,000 real and 5,000 fake).

2. Feature Extraction:

- **Profile-based features:** Number of friends, posts, and profile completeness.
- **Content-based features:** Analysis of posts and comments using NLP techniques like sentiment analysis, word embeddings, and topic modeling.
- **Behavioral features:** Posting frequency, interaction patterns.

3. Model Training:

- Split the dataset into training and testing sets (e.g., 80% training, 20% testing).
- Train various machine learning models such as Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, Random Forest, SVM, and neural networks.
- Use NLP techniques like TF-IDF, BERT embeddings for text data.

4. Evaluation Metrics:

- Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score, ROC-AUC.

Figure 2: Graph for accuracy

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we present a Driving Decision Strategy to help drivers make better decisions. It visualizes the autonomous vehicle's driving and consumables situations to offer drivers, and it employs a genetic algorithm based on collected data to determine the optimal driving strategy depending on the slope and curve of the road it is traveling on. Experiments reviewing data from an autonomous car were performed to prove the DDS's viability by identifying the best driving strategy. Comparatively accurate, the DDS is 40% quicker at determining the optimal driving approach. More importantly, DDS is 20 percent quicker at determining the optimal driving approach and is 22 percent more accurate than RF. The DDS is the go-to when precision and timeliness are of the utmost importance. Because the DDS just uploads the minimum amount of information required for a genetic algorithm analysis on the cloud, it can determine the best driving strategy for the car much more quickly than previous approaches. These evaluations were conducted in a simulated setting utilizing personal computers with subpar graphics processing units. In the future, it will be important to put DDS to the test in a real-world setting. Designers with experience in this area should also work to enhance the aesthetic elements.

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